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FORMING THE SKILLS OF MONOLOGUE AND DIALOGUE SPEECH IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the peculiarities of forming students' monologue and dialogue speech skills. The significance of the issue teaching future specialists to speak a foreign language in modern conditions. The article presents examples of exercises aimed at teaching students each type of monologue and dialogue speech. The article presents examples of exercises aimed at teaching students to each type of monologue and dialogue speech. The features of creation of speech situations in the classroom, the statement that the full development of speaking skills is possible provided that students are taught all types of monologue and dialogue speech. When forming the ability of dialogue speaking, students master the types of dialogue: modal and regulative, which can be standard and free.

Keywords: foreign language teaching, speaking skills, monologue speech, dialogue speech, university students.

Buranova Lola Uktamovna

“Ingliz tili va adabiyoti” kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi
Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti

MONOLOGIK VA DIALOGIK NUTQIY KO'NIKMALARINI CHET TILDA SHAKLLANTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada talabalarning monologik va dialogik nutqi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Bo'lajak mutaxassislarni zamonaviy sharoitda chet tilida so'zlashishga o'rgatish masalasining ahamiyati asoslab berilgan. Darsda nutqiy vaziyatlarni yaratish xususiyatlari ko'rsatilgan. Bayonotda, shuningdek, talabalarga monologik va dialogik nutqning barcha turlarini o'rgatish sharti bilan nutq qobiliyatlarini har tomonlama rivojlantirish mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan. Dialogik nutq qobiliyatini shakllantirishda talabalar dialogning turlarini o'zlashtiradilar: diktal, modal va tartibga soluvchi, ular standart va erkin bo'lishi mumkin. Maqolada talabalarni monologik va dialogik nutqning har bir turiga o'rgatishga qaratilgan mashqlar misollari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tilini o'qitish, nutq, monolog nutq, dialogik nutq, universitet talabalari.

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ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НАВЫКОВ МОНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ НА ИНОСТРАННОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируются особенности формирования умений монологической и диалогической речи студентов. Обосновывается значимость вопроса обучения говорению будущих специалистов на иностранном языке в современных условиях. Представлены особенности создания речевых ситуаций на занятиях. Также представлено утверждение о том, что полноценное освоение умений говорения возможно при условии обучения студентов всем видам монологической и диалогической речи. При формировании умения диалогического говорения студенты осваивают виды диалога: диктальный, модальный и регулятивный, которые могут быть стандартными и свободными. В статье представлены примеры упражнений, направленных на обучение студентов каждому виду монологической и диалогической речи.

Ключевые слова иноязычное обучение, умения говорения, монологическая речь, диалогическая речь, студенты вузов.

Introduction

At different stages of the formation of foreign language teaching methodology, the importance of speaking skills varied significantly. Until relatively recently, when teaching a foreign language, the emphasis was primarily on teaching reading as the objectively most relevant skill for those times. This approach to teaching enabled students to have access to professional literature in a foreign language. Speaking skills were considered as a secondary task of learning due to the limited possibility of communication in a foreign language. These skills were formed mainly by memorizing or retelling large professional texts. However, modernity dictates completely different requirements for the training of specialists. The ability to read in itself (isolated from general speech competence) has ceased to be a value.

With the help of electronic translators, texts of any volume and any subject are quickly and at a sufficient level for understanding translated into the native language of a specialist. Today, a foreign language in the professional field is required equally as a tool for working with foreign-language sources, and as a tool for professional communication: negotiating, exchanging experience, cooperation, participating in conferences and symposiums, implementing international projects, promoting copyright developments, etc. From the foregoing, it also follows that the tasks that are set when teaching a foreign language at a university are many times more complex and complex than the previous ones. To achieve them, there is an obvious need to intensify the educational process and apply effective methods to prepare students for real communication in a foreign language. A key element in preparing students for communication is the formation of monologue and dialogue speaking skills. Before analyzing the specifics of the formation of each of these skills to students, let us consider those of their characteristics that should be taken into account when teaching both monologue and dialogue speech.

Materials and methods

The purpose of teaching speaking is to develop students' ability to carry out oral speech communication in accordance with their real needs and interests in a variety of socially determined situations. An important characteristic of speaking is its dependence on the conditions in which it takes place, that is, on the extralinguistic context (the purpose and conditions of communication, topics and content, the characteristic originality of the participants in speaking, etc.) [1]. These conditions form the basis of speech situations. In his study “Language, Speech, Speech Activity”, A. A. Leontiev defines a speech situation as “a set of conditions, speech and non-speech, necessary and

sufficient in order to carry out a speech action according to the planned plan” [2]. In a foreign language class, the speech situation is purposefully created by the teacher. In this case, the imagination of students plays a special role, since the specified conditions, as a rule, are fictitious. Students imagine themselves in different roles and places, solve imaginary problems, achieve externally non-deterministic communicative tasks. These simulated (speech) situations will contribute to the development of speaking skills if:

- they reflect the real situations of the present, which are lived by students and therefore are relevant for students;
- have an element of fiction, absurdity, humor, which causes an emotional response;
 - touch on topics of personal importance for students;
- raise problematic, ambiguous questions that encourage discussion.

Results

Let's move on to the analysis of the features of the formation of the skills of monologue speech. Compared to dialogic speech, the monologue is characterized by relative continuity, greater expansion, arbitrariness (planning), consistency and focus on creating a product - a monologue statement. When speaking about the features of teaching monologue speech, T. A. Baeva emphasizes that earlier attention was paid mainly to teaching monologue utterance in the format of reproduction of large texts of a professional nature. Now the training of monologue speech should consist in the formation of skills to create various genres of monologue texts: communication of information of a professional nature, presentation of a report, extended statement during the discussion, discussion with and without preliminary preparation [3]. Monologue speech is classified according to a number of criteria, depending on:

- content: description, message (story), reasoning;
- degree of independence: reproductive, reproductive-productive, productive speech;
- degree of preparedness: prepared, partially prepared, unprepared speech [4, p. 38]

It should be noted that each type of monologue speech must be developed purposefully. If in a foreign language class speech exercises are mainly performed to develop a reproductive type of speech, then without the necessary practice, the student will not be able to successfully perform the tasks of productive monologue speaking. If priority is given to one form (for example, the communication of information), then the description or reasoning in a foreign language will cause difficulties for students. The idea that prepared speech is a step towards unprepared speech, which itself will appear among students at certain points in their learning, is also false [5, p. 93].

A prepared speech should reasonably be considered as an independent type of monologue speech, typical for conferences, meetings and other forms of business communication that require preliminary preparation and planning. Unprepared speech as one of the types of monologue (the most difficult for many students) should also be purposefully taught - the need for it arises both in everyday communication situations and in the field of professional activity.

Therefore, the recommendation in teaching monologue speech in a foreign language is the variety of speech exercises used, aimed at the formation of various types of monologue speech, as well as work on those types of monologue that cause the greatest difficulty for students. Let us give examples of speech exercises used in foreign language classes to teach various types of monologue.

1. The description is aimed at presenting the characteristics of an object and involves a presentation of the features (quantitative, qualitative, structural, functional) and properties of the described object [6]. After introducing lexical units on the topic, reading texts, listening to audio texts or watching a video where students get acquainted with examples of describing the system under study, students can be offered the following speech exercises:

- reproductive. Based on a pre-prepared plan for the read text, tell your listener about the functional system being studied. In your speech, intentionally make three factual errors. Your listener's task is to identify these errors and correct them;
- reproductive and productive. Based on previously studied information (texts, audio and video materials). Using the prepared scheme, conduct an exciting mini-lecture for your listener / listeners. At the end of the lecture, ask the listeners questions to check their attentiveness;

- productive. Imagine that you are a scientist / alien / five-year-old child / rector of a university, etc. Tell on behalf of this character so that your speech, information presented, gestures and facial expressions correspond to the hero. (Roles can be drawn by students from a set of cards or can be invented by students themselves for each other.

2. A message (story, narration) is defined as a statement about any event in its temporal sequence, that is, this form of speech is distinguished by dynamism due to the presence of sequential actions. The usefulness of a speech statement in the form of a message depends not only on their possession of a certain set of lexical units of a professional nature and a number of grammatical constructions, but also on the ability to maintain the logic of the narrative, using, among other things, the forms of communication of statements. Here are examples of speech exercises (based on the TV series watched by students) that are performed in the message format:

- reproductive. Watch the episode at home and prepare a list of keywords that will help you uncover its plot. Using a list of words, tell the listener the plot of the series so that he also wants to watch this series (different students prepare assignments for different series);
- reproductive and productive. Watch the first half of the series at home (20 min). Make a plan that reflects the development of the plot, and also come up with your own version of the end of the series. Tell your listener your version of the plot of the series and listen to his version. Then for the next lesson, watch the second half of the series, compare your version with the actual ending;
- productive. Watch fragments of the series (which were watched at home) without sound, or, conversely, listen to a fragment of the series without a picture. Tell your partner your assumptions about: 1) where the action takes place, 2) who is involved in it, 3) what is happening, 4) what happened before and will happen after.

3. Reasoning is an oral presentation, explanation, confirmation of the put forward thought. It provides the validity of actions, the definition of their cause-and-effect relationships, the argument for accepting or rejecting ideas. The ability of reasoning in a foreign language lesson can be developed when discussing controversial topics or problematic situations in the professional activities of a teacher. Consider examples of exercises that encourage students to reason in a foreign language:

- reproductive. Read the text about the difficult decision the teacher had to make. Prepare and present a story to your listener about this decision and the reasons for making it. Then listen to another story (on the same topic) read earlier by your partner. Discuss your attitude to each story;
- reproductive and productive. Debate on the theme "Higher education, pros and cons". Prepare arguments and their rationale based on the literature you have read to support your position. During the game, present your arguments, evidence, and also give counterarguments to the speech of opponents and draw general conclusions about the game;
- productive. Read the text where the teacher describes 7 reasons why it is better not to become teachers. Imagine that your listener is the author of the article you read.

Discussion

Try to convince him otherwise by arguing your speech. The teacher can regulate the degree of preparedness in all the presented speech exercises depending on whether the exercise is given for home preparation, whether it is prepared in class for a limited period of time or performed without preparation.

Consider the features of the formation of the skills of dialogical speech in a foreign language. The relevance of the issue of the formation of dialogical speech is due to the opportunities that students have due to communication in a foreign language.

Such opportunities are: the implementation of professional communication, the exchange of work experience. Defining the characteristics of the dialogue, V. A. Buchbinder points out that "the need for constant switching, as well as the combination of productive and receptive functions, allows us to consider dialogue as a special, independent, functionally multidirectional, combined type of oral speech activity, in which it is inappropriate to separate speaking and listening and it is advisable to see in it, although complex, consisting of multidirectional operations, but in essence, a single function - conducting a conversation. It is very difficult for students and requires a special approach in teaching" [5, p.100]. When teaching dialogue speech, the formation of speaking and listening skills,

switching between these types of speech activity, as well as the ability to conduct a conversation are equally significant. The latter is manifested in the fact that the dialogic text is a coherent speech formation both at the level of the utterance of each individual partner of the dialogue, and at the level of the utterances of both speakers. The connection between the replicas of the entire dialogic unity should be considered not as a way of linking replicas, but as a single semantic connection [7]. In order for the process of communication to take place, contact must be established between the participants. Contact is understood as “the establishment, preservation or strengthening, maintenance of ties and relations of individual or social-mass in small and large social groups” [8, p. 27]. The ability to establish contact with an interlocutor is initially formed in students when communicating in their native language, and then the already formed skills are transferred when communicating in a foreign language. However, practice shows that for many students this skill is not formed at a sufficient level in their native language. Establishing contact in a foreign language is even more difficult due to the limited language resources. To develop this skill, we consider it expedient to create conditions for communication of students with a large number of different language partners, that is, the use of the form of work "a pair of shifts". This form assumes that, while performing a communicative task, students can freely move around the classroom, independently changing communication partners in accordance with their individual speed of completing the task, or make the transition to a new partner in a given logic and within a given time frame. In addition, it is important to teach students the existing speech and extralinguistic strategies for establishing contact and to increase the level of awareness of students on this issue. When teaching dialogic speech, the existence of various types of dialogues should also be taken into account. They are classified according to:

- structures: microdialogues (based on the same type of dialogic units that are in a logical and semantic relationship) and thematic macrodialogues (include several microdialogues);
- degrees are free: standard (with clearly defined roles, involving the use of stereotypical language material) and free [4, p. 38];
- psychological attitudes of partners: dictal (survey, exchange of information), modal (argument, discussion), regulatory (planning, instruction, persuasion) [9].

Conclusion

To sum up, as in the case of monologue speech, for the full formation of the ability of dialogue speech, it is important to purposefully develop each of the presented types with a gradual increase in the complexity and complexity of the built dialogues. In the classroom, communicative (role-playing and business) games, discussions, brainstorming, case analysis can be held.

Thus, teaching monologue and dialogue speaking in a foreign language is a long and step-by-step process that takes into account a number of features of the formation of the discussed skills:

1. It is necessary to create speech situations that encourage students to actively communicate in a foreign language.

2. The effectiveness of the educational process will depend on the presence of a stable positive emotional attitude of students to speaking a foreign language, which is formed as part of the educational process

3. Modern social conditions require specialists to fully master the skills of speaking. This becomes possible when teaching students all types of monologue (description, communication, reasoning; reproductive, reproductive-productive, productive; prepared, partially prepared, unprepared) and dialogic (microdialogues and macrodialogues; standard and free; dictal, modal, regulative) speaking.

4. The success of communication in a foreign language depends on the ability to establish contact with the interlocutor, which should also be taught to students in the classroom.

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